

CHALLENGES EXPERIENCED AND LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF ACADEMIC PERSONNEL WITH THE CURRENT DELIVERABLES MONITORING SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15212485>

ABSTRACT

Academic personnel are involved in numerous responsibilities while working in educational institutions. One of these responsibilities is submitting the required deliverables. This study aims to determine the challenges experienced and the level of satisfaction of academic personnel with the current deliverables monitoring system. The researchers surveyed two hundred sixty-two academic personnel from various colleges and departments of the university using the researcher-made questionnaire. Utilizing purposive sampling, participants in the survey were chosen based on their roles in the academic community. Content validation of the questionnaire was done by five experts. Informed consent and an ethics permit were obtained before the implementation of the survey. The findings revealed that the top three deliverables were grade sheets, course syllabi, and examination papers. The top three challenges experienced by the academic personnel were the repetitive submissions of the same documents, difficulty in performance tracking, and difficulty in tracking submission progress. The level of satisfaction with the current deliverables monitoring system was highly satisfactory for all processes. However, for improvement, the academic personnel suggested a web-based automation system for the deliverables' monitoring. Hence, understanding the information revealed from the study can be an essential prerequisite for proposing an improved and better system that will boost academic personnel's productivity and performance.

Keywords: *Deliverables, Traditional Monitoring, Document Monitoring, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The effective monitoring of academic personnel deliverables is essential to the success of educational institution accreditations. Deliverables monitoring plays a crucial role in ensuring effective documentation of evidence for overall institutional performance toward academic excellence and advancement. Academic personnel are responsible for various academic activities (Sridhar et al., 2010). These activities involve the submission of deliverables, developing teaching materials, engaging in teaching-learning activities, participating in professional development training (Shagrir, 2013), engaging in service learning and outreach programs, and conducting research projects (Paudel, 2021) for presentations, publications, and other scholarly works (Podolyanchuk, 2020).

However, the challenges associated with the submission and monitoring of these deliverables can be significantly difficult, especially when relying on traditional or outdated systems. To determine these challenges and other factors and to propose better solutions, research must be conducted. Hence, the researchers decided to investigate the challenges experienced and the level of satisfaction of academic personnel with the current deliverables monitoring system in one of the universities in the Philippines, which is important to develop a better monitoring system.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine the challenges experienced and to assess the level of satisfaction of academic personnel with the current deliverables monitoring system. By determining the academic personnel concerns, the study seeks to provide insights into the current practices and potential improvements to propose enhancements that will ensure a more efficient and effective monitoring system.

The specific objectives of the research are the following:

- 1) identify the types of required faculty deliverables;
- 2) determine the problems experienced by the academic personnel in the current deliverable monitoring system; and
- 3) determine the level of satisfaction with the current deliverables monitoring system.

The areas of investigation will include the challenges experienced and the overall satisfaction level of academic personnel on the current deliverable monitoring system. The findings of this research are expected to help understand the problems experienced by academic personnel, which will contribute to the improvement or development of new monitoring systems, ultimately leading to better faculty performance and institutional success.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the quantitative approach, which utilized a questionnaire for the survey method in gathering data (Dalati & Marx Gómez, 2018). As shown in Figure 1, the framework used in the study was composed of the following process: identification of participants of the study and data to be collected, determination of the sample size and sampling technique, formulation and validation of the research instrument, implementation of the survey, analysis of data, and presentation of the results. The literature review was conducted to gain insights into the previous research conducted on the topic, the data-gathering process, and the possible items or variables for the questionnaires.

Figure 1

The Framework of the Study

The Participants and Sampling

The participants were identified based on their involvement in the current monitoring system. The identified stakeholders were the academic personnel, including faculty members, the office staff, the academic supervisors, and the deans from various colleges/departments of one university in Iloilo City. The sampling technique used in the survey was purposive sampling. The total number of participants who responded to the survey was 262 out of 760 total academic personnel of the university, matching the required sample size computed using Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error (Nurkholis et al., 2024). The formula is $n = N / (1 + N(e^2))$, where n = sample size, N = total population size, and e = margin of error.

The Research Instruments

The research-made questionnaire was designed and developed (Torchiano et al., 2017) to gather data from existing problems and practices of the deliverables monitoring system. The questionnaire was composed of mixed questions: closed-ended and open-ended questions. After finalizing the questionnaire, it was then evaluated by five (5) experts for content validity before implementation.

Data Gathering Process

The data gathering was done within six (6) weeks. The survey was conducted online via Google Forms and paper-based via printed hard copies. The Google Forms link was sent to participants through their university email addresses. The printed questionnaires were sent to the participants through their college offices with a predetermined number of copies and instructions. The participants' answers to the survey from the online Google forms were collected via a Google Sheet that was stored in the cloud. The accomplished paper-based questionnaires were collected from each college seven (7) working days after they were distributed. Then, the survey questionnaires' answers were encoded into the Google sheet to consolidate research data into one single file. The Google sheet was downloaded, and the data were cleaned for analysis.

Data Analysis and Presentation

The survey results were coded, processed, and summarized using SPSS statistical software. The survey results were analyzed using descriptive statistics (Ariastuti & Wahyudin, 2022), such as frequency, percentage, rank, mean, and standard deviation, to identify trends and patterns in the participants' responses. The results of the survey were presented in table format.

RESULTS

The survey results presented the demographics of the participants, the types of deliverables required in a college/department, challenges experienced by the faculty, and the level of satisfaction with the current deliverables monitoring system of the university.

Demographics of the Participants

Table 1 shows the distribution of the participants according to type and gender. There was a total sample (n) of 262 (100 percent) participants from the 760 total number of academic personnel for the entire university. As to the type of participants, there were 236 faculty members (90 percent); 19 (7 percent) academic supervisors; 4 (2 percent) office staff; and 3 (1 percent) deans/principals. In terms of gender, 83 (32) were males, and 179 (68 percent) were females.

Table 1

Distribution of the Participants According to Type and Gender, n=262

Participant Type	Frequency	Percentage
Faculty member	236	90
Academic supervisor	19	7
Office staff	4	2
Dean/Principal	3	1

Total	262	100
Gender		
Male	83	32
Female	179	68%
Total	262	100%

Table 2 shows the distribution of the participants according to department and employment. In terms of the participants' college/department, both College of Commerce (COC) and College of Pharmacy and Medical Technology (CPMT) have 18 (7 percent); College of Liberal Arts, Sciences and Education (CLASE) has 35 (14 percent); College of Technology (COT) has 29 (11 percent); College of Nursing, Nutrition and Dietetics (CNND) has 89 (34 percent); Center for Religious and Studies (CRS) has 9 (3 percent); Senior High School (SHS) Department has 22 (8 percent); Junior High School (JHS) Department has 23 (9 percent); and Basic Education Department-Elementary has 19 (7 percent). In terms of employment, there were 101 (39 percent) regular, 42 (16 percent) probationary, and 119 (45 percent) part-time participants.

Table 2

Distribution of the Participants according to Department and Employment, n=262

Department	Frequency	Percentage
College of Commerce (COC)	18	7
College of Pharmacy and Medical Technology (CPMT)	18	7
College of Liberal Arts and Education (CLASE)	35	14
College of Technology (COT)	29	11
College of Nursing, Nutrition, and Dietetics (CNND)	89	34
Center of Religious Studies (CRS)	9	3
Senior High School (SHS) Department	22	8
Junior High School (JHS) Department	23	9
Basic Education Department-Elementary (BED-Elem)	19	7
Total	262	100
Employment		
Regular	101	39
Probationary	42	16
Part-time	119	45
Total	262	100

Types of Deliverables Required in a College/Department

Data in Table 3 shows the results of the survey using the rank. Grade sheets were the first deliverable, as indicated by the participants with 230, R = 1; Course Syllabus is the second with 220, R = 2; Examination papers were third with 218, R=3. The last 3 deliverables required were the Community Outreach Report with 129, R = 12; the Service-Learning Report with 103, R = 13; and Checked Lab Manuals with 94, R = 14.

Table 3*Types of Deliverables Required in the College/Department, n=262*

Type of Deliverables	Frequency	Rank
1. Grade Sheets	230	1
2. Course Syllabus	220	2
3. Examination Papers	218	3
4. Certificates of Attended Seminar/Training	217	4
5. Philippine Regulation Commission (PRC) ID (if applicable)	211	5
6. Table of Specification	209	6
7. Class Records	201	7
8. Consultation Report	183	8
9. Student Outputs	181	9
10. Lesson Modules	178	10
11. Checked Examination Papers (samples only)	158	11
12. Community Outreach Report	129	12
13. Service-Learning Report	103	13
14. Checked Lab Manuals (samples only)	94	14

The Existing Method for Monitoring the Faculty Deliverables

Data in Table 4 shows the results of the survey for the existing method for monitoring faculty deliverables. The semi-automated method is the first with 206 responses (79 percent); Fully-automated is the second with 40 responses (15 percent); and the manual is the last with 16 responses (6 percent). The

Table 4*The Existing Method for Faculty Deliverables Monitoring, n=262*

Method	Frequency	Percentage
Manual	16	6
Semi-Automated	206	79
Fully-automated	40	15
Total	262	100

Challenges Experienced by the Faculty in the Current Deliverables Monitoring System

Table 5 reflects the responses to whether or not the participants experienced problems in the current deliverable monitoring system. One hundred eighty-two (182, 70 percent) responded with a yes. Only 80 (30 percent) answered with a no.

Table 5

Challenges Experienced in the Current Deliverable Monitoring System, n=262

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	182	70
No	80	30
Total	262	100

When asked further, which of the following are the problems encountered, Table 6 shows the nature of the problems experienced in the current deliverables monitoring system. “Repetitive submissions of the same documents” emerged as the first problem with 122, R = 1; “Difficulty in Performance tracking (completed or not) with 94, R = 2; “Difficulty in tracking submission progress with 89, R=3. The last three include “Difficulty in updating submissions” with 66, R=7; and “Difficulty in tracking deadline” and “Difficulty in retrieving submitted documents” with 62, R=7.5.

Table 6

Current problems experienced with the deliverables monitoring system, n=262

Problems	Frequency	Rank
1. Repetitive submissions of the same documents	122	1
2. Difficulty in performance tracking (completed or not)	94	2
3. Difficulty in tracking submission progress	89	3
4. Missing submitted documents when needed	79	4
5. No centralized storage	68	5
6. Difficulty in updating submissions	66	6
7. Difficulty in tracking the deadline	62	7.5
8. Difficulty in retrieving submitted documents	62	7.5

Level of satisfaction with the current deliverable monitoring system

Data in Table 7 shows the level of satisfaction of the participants with the current deliverables monitoring system. The mean and standard deviation results reflect that the participants are highly satisfied with the current deliverables monitoring system, with the means ranging from 3.48 - 3.68 and SD 0.78 - 0.87.

Table 7

Level of Satisfaction with the Current Deliverables Monitoring System, n=262

Process	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. Submission process	3.68	0.79	Highly Satisfied
2. Checking process	3.61	0.77	Highly Satisfied
3. Verification process	3.59	0.83	Highly Satisfied
4. Acceptance process	3.69	0.79	Highly Satisfied
5. Approval process	3.62	0.81	Highly Satisfied
6. Storing process	3.50	0.87	Highly Satisfied
7. Retrieval process	3.48	0.87	Highly Satisfied
8. Reporting process	3.60	0.78	Highly Satisfied

*Legend: 1-1.8 – Not Satisfied 1.81-2.6 – Less Satisfied 2.61-3.4- Satisfied
3.41-4.2- Highly Satisfied 4.21-5 – Very Highly Satisfied*

Agreement to Improve the Deliverables Monitoring System

Table 8 shows the responses to the agreement on whether or not to improve the current deliverables monitoring system using an automated web-based system. All of the participants of two hundred sixty-two (262, 100 percent) responded with a yes. None (0 percent) answered with a no.

Table 8

Agreement to Improve the Deliverables Monitoring Using an Automated Web-based System, n=262

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	262	100
No	0	0
Total	262	100

DISCUSSION

In educational institutions, academic personnel need to meet the submission of their deliverables for several reasons. Fulfilling professional responsibility, submitting the requirements for performance incentives, and submitting the teaching-learning outputs for accreditation/certification purposes are examples of these reasons. The deliverables monitoring system aims to simplify the process of tracking and evaluating faculty performance against predefined goals. However, the implementation and use of such systems come with their own set of challenges and varying levels of satisfaction among the stakeholders.

In Table 1, the distribution of survey participants showed that the majority were faculty members, but all types of academic personnel were represented according to their roles. In Table 2, there were 6 colleges and 4 departments that participated in the survey. The College of Nursing, Nutrition, and Dietetics (CNND) had the highest number of participants, while the Center of Religious Studies had the lowest number of participants. In terms of employment, the part-time category had the highest number of participants.

In Table 3, the top 1 deliverable was grade sheets. This document is submitted at the end of the semester/year as it is important for the student's promotion from one level to the next level. It is followed by the course syllabus submitted at the start of the semester. The next was the examination papers submitted to the academic supervisor for checking before the examination implementation. PRC ID is required for all faculty teaching professional courses with board examinations. All of the listed deliverables are required, but their priority varies from one college/department to another.

From the results of the existing monitoring method in Table 4, the semi-automated method has the highest frequency. The deliverables are submitted either in soft copies or hard copies. From Table 5, seventy percent of the survey participants admitted that they experienced problems. Table 6 shows that the top five (5) challenges of faculty are repetitive submissions of the same documents, difficulty in performance tracking if the submission is complete or not, submission progress (if it is approved or not), missing submitted documents when needed, and no centralized storage. Examples of documents that are submitted repetitively are the syllabus and PRC ID, which are submitted at the start of classes and end of the semester. These problems take a lot of time, affecting faculty productivity and performance (Sridhar et al., 2010).

The academic personnel were highly satisfied with all processes listed in Table 7 for the current deliverables monitoring system. These processes include submission, checking, verification, acceptance, approval, storage, and retrieval processes. Each process was rated using the 5-point Likert scale, and then the mean score was computed for each process to determine its descriptive interpretation. These processes are included in the full cycle of the current deliverables monitoring system.

Despite this high level of satisfaction, the academic personnel still wanted to have a better deliverable monitoring system, as shown in Table 8, wherein all 262 participants agreed

that a web-based automated system (Jaquilmo & Sarmiento, 2023) would improve overall academic performance (Mather & Bam, 2025).

Conclusions

In conclusion, the investigation of the challenges experienced and the level of satisfaction with the current deliverables monitoring system has revealed important insights. The findings provide the extent of academic personnel's experiences with the current deliverables monitoring system. There are fourteen types of deliverables identified that are being monitored. The top three of these are grade sheets, course syllabi, and examination papers. Seventy percent of the academic personnel confirmed that they experienced eight types of problems. These challenges often hinder the effective monitoring of deliverables, leading to frustration and decreased productivity among faculty members in the university. However, the study revealed a high level of satisfaction with the current deliverables monitoring system among academic personnel. This system uses a semi-automated method that allows deliverable submissions of both digital copies and hard copies that need more physical space for storage. Hence, a fully automated web-based system can make the deliverables monitoring better and more effective for continuous improvement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, a more detailed analysis of the current deliverable monitoring system is needed to identify good practices and necessary procedures that can be adopted for system improvement. Further, a study to determine the needs and expectations of the stakeholders for designing the new system is recommended. Conducting a need assessment for a future deliverables monitoring system related to the web-based system can be done, including the following essential considerations:

- 1) Participants' preferences related to the automated deliverables monitoring system
- 2) policy and guidelines of the school on deliverable submission requirements
- 3) review of the existing practice for approval of deliverable submission
- 4) system features such as user interface, seamless design, user and activity logs, security mechanism, and dashboards.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethics permit was secured from the university ethics review committee before the implementation of the survey. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the data-gathering process. Participants' confidentiality and anonymity were ensured throughout the research process. Participants were allowed to withdraw from the survey at any time. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study. Data was securely

stored and only accessed by authorized research team members and was used for research purposes only. Plagiarism was strictly enforced.

Acknowledgments

A special thank you to the University of San Agustin for providing us with the necessary resources and facilities to carry out our research and to Fr. Ian Ragodon, O.S.A., the former Vice President for Administration and Finance, for approving the release of our research budget. Also, the researchers are very grateful to all academic personnel who participated and contributed to the success of this research and the academic administrators of the university for their support in this endeavor.

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